

[Jour. Indian Chem. Soc., Vol. 26 No 1, 1949]

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF
COMPLEX METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES
PART VIII. THERMOMETRIC STUDY OF THE
COMPOSITION OF CADMIUM FERRICYANIDE

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The composition of cadmium ferricyanide has been studied by the thermometric titrations of cadmium sulphate solutions with K_3FeCy_6 solutions, both by direct and reverse methods, in aqueous and aqueous alcoholic media. The results support the constitution of the compound as $KCd_{10}(Fe^{III}Cy_6)_7$, arrived at earlier by the conductometric method.

Studies on the composition of cadmium ferricyanide have been further extended. The thermometric studies support the results of the conductometric studies (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 349). The compound $KCd_{10}(Fe^{III}Cy_6)_7$ is formed, but the composition is also influenced by hydrolysis and adsorption.

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EXPERIMENTAL

'AnalaR' (B. D. H.) reagents were used. Preparation of the standard solution has been described in Part VII (*loc. cit.*). The thermometric titration arrangement was similar to the one used previously (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 487 ; 1948, 25, 185). With different concentration of the two salt solutions, the titrations were carried out by the direct and the reverse methods, *i.e.*, when cadmium sulphate from the burette was added to potassium ferricyanide taken in the thermos flask, and *vice versa*. The titrations were also carried out in presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20% by volume.

$M/4.82$ solution of cadmium sulphate would be referred as A/1-solution of cadmium sulphate, and $M/5.06$ solution of potassium ferricyanide as A/1- K_3FeCy_6 solution.

Control experiments, as communicated in part VII (*loc. cit.*) of this series, showed that inspite of its oxidising nature, potassium ferricyanide had no action on alcohol under the conditions of the experiment. Hence the titre values do not suffer any change due to this,

Direct Thermometric Titrations

TABLE I

A/10-K₃FeCy₆ = 20 c. c.
Alcohol = nil (curve 1).

A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.035°
0.8	0.065
1.6	0.125
2.4	0.195
3.2	0.255
4.0	0.290°
4.8	0.325

TABLE II

A/10-K₃FeCy₆ = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c. c. (curve 2).

A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.2 c.c.	0.020°
0.8	0.080
1.4	0.140
1.8	0.175
2.0	0.200
2.4	0.240
3.2	0.280

TABLE III

A/10-K₃FeCy₆ = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c. (curve 3).

A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.2 c.c.	0.025°
0.4	0.050
0.8	0.095
1.4	0.185
1.8	0.245
2.2	0.305
2.8	0.365

TABLE IV

A/10-K₃FeCy₆ = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil (curve 4).

A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.080°
1.2	0.070
1.6	0.100
2.4	0.180
3.6	0.245
4.4	0.310
5.2	0.365
6.4	0.430

TABLE V

A/10-K₃FeCy₆ = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c.c. (curve 5).

A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.015°
1.2	0.045
2.0	0.075
2.8	0.105
3.2	0.120
4.0	0.150
5.2	0.190
6.4	0.220

TABLE VI

A/10 K₃FeCy₆ = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c. (curve 6).

A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.080°
1.2	0.120
2.0	0.205
2.8	0.285
3.2	0.320
4.4	0.425
4.8	0.455°
5.6	0.495

Reverse Thermometric Titrations

TABLE VII

A/10-CdSO₄ = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil. (curve 7).

A/2-K ₃ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.2 c.c.	0.010°
0.6	0.040
1.0	0.070
1.4	0.105
1.8	0.140
2.2	0.175
2.6	0.210°
2.8	0.225
3.2	0.245

TABLE VIII

A/10-CdSO₄ = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2 c. c. (curve 8)

A/2-K ₃ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.2 c.c.	0.010°
0.6	0.085
1.0	0.070
1.2	0.085
1.6	0.120
1.8	0.135
2.6	0.200
3.0	0.220
3.2	0.230

TABLE IX

A/10-CdSO₄ = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c. c. (curve 9)

A/2-K ₃ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.2 c.c.	0.010°
0.6	0.050
0.8	0.065
1.2	0.100
1.6	0.140
2.0	0.180
2.6	0.220
2.8	0.225°
3.0	0.240

TABLE X

A/10-CdSO₄ = 20 c.c.
Alcohol = nil (curve 10).

A/4-K ₃ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.010°
0.8	0.025
2.0	0.070
3.2	0.120
4.4	0.170
5.6	0.220
6.4	0.250
6.8	0.280

TABLE XI

A/10-CdSO₄ soln. = 18 c.c.
Alcohol = 2c.c (curve 11).

A/4-K ₃ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.010°
0.8	0.020
2.0	0.060
3.2	0.125
4.4	0.185
5.6	0.235
6.0	0.245
6.4	0.255

TABLE XII

A/10-CdSO₄ soln. = 16 c.c.
Alcohol = 4 c.c (curve 12).

A/4-K ₃ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.4 c.c.	0.040°
0.8	0.080
2.0	0.205
3.2	0.315
3.6	0.350
4.8	0.445
5.8	0.495
6.0	0.515

TABLE XIII

Direct thermometric titrations

A/1-Cadmium sulphate and A/10-potassium ferricyanide. Conc. ratio (n) = 10 : 1.

A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆ in the cell.	Alcohol added.	CdSO ₄ reqd. for K ₃ FeCy ₆ in the cell.	CdSO ₄ calc. for 20 c.c. A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆	Equiv. vol of A/10-CdSO ₄ .	Curve No
10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	2.74 c.c.	2.74 c.c.	27.4 c.c.	1
9	1.0	2.44	2.71	27.1	2
8	2.0	2.16	2.70	27.0	3

A/2-Cadmium sulphate and A/10-potassium ferricyanide, Conc. ratio (n) = 5:1.

10	0.0 c.c.	5.52 c.c.	5.52 c.c.	27.60 c.c.	4
9	1.0	4.92	5.47	27.35	5
8	2.0	4.32	5.40	27.00	6

Reverse thermometric titrations

A/2-Potassium ferricyanide and A/10-cadmium sulphate. Conc. ratio (n) = 5:1.

A/10-CdSO ₄ in the cell.	Alcohol added.	K ₃ FeCy ₆ reqd. for CdSO ₄ in the cell	K ₃ FeCy ₆ calc. for 20 c.c. of A/10-CdSO ₄ .	Equiv. vol. of A/10-K ₃ FeCy ₆ .	Curve No.
10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	2.74 c.c.	2.74 c.c.	13.7 c.c.	7
9	1.0	2.52	2.80	14.0	8
8	2.0	2.32	2.90	14.5	9

Conc. ratio (n) = 5 : 1.

A/4-Potassium ferricyanide and A/10 cadmium sulphate Conc. ratio (n) = 2.5 : 1.

10 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	5.48 c.c.	5.48 c.c.	13.7 c.c.	10
9	1.0	5.00	5.56	13.9	11
8	2.0	4.64	5.80	14.5	12

DISCUSSION

In continuation of our previous studies on the composition of cadmium ferricyanide by the conductometric method (Part VII, *loc. cit.*), the thermometric study of the compound has been carried out. The nature of the discrepancies between the theoretical and observed titre values, in the aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic media in the direct and reverse titrations are similar.

From the strengths of the solutions of cadmium sulphate ($M/4.82$), and potassium ferricyanide ($M/5.06$), the theoretical titre values for 20 c.c. of potassium ferricyanide solution for the formation of the compounds $\text{KCd}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)$, $\text{Cd}_3^-(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_2$ and $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_7$, in the direct titration are 19.04, 28.5 and 27.1 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution respectively. The theoretical titre values for 20 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution for the formation of the same compounds in the reverse titrations are respectively 21.0, 14.04 and 14.74 c.c. of potassium ferricyanide solution.

The observed titre values for 20 c.c. of potassium ferricyanide solution in aqueous medium is 27.4 to 27.6 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution, which, in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol, decreases and very nearly approaches the theoretical¹ titre value required for the formation of the compound $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_7$. Taking into consideration the hydrolysability of such compounds, as has already been observed (Part VII), the titre values in direct titrations in aqueous medium would be slightly higher than the theoretical titre value. In presence of increasing amounts of alcohol, the titre values would decrease, as the hydrolysis would be checked to some extent. The observed titre values then in aqueous-alcoholic medium would approach the theoretical titre value for the complex which is actually formed. From this consideration it is obvious that the compound $\text{Cd}_3(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_2$ is not formed as the observed titre value in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol recedes further from the theoretical titre value. The values, on the other hand, support the formation of the compound $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_7$.

From the view point of hydrolysis, the observed titre values in aqueous medium in case of reverse titrations would be lower than the theoretical one, and in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol they would gradually increase, and approach the theoretical value required for the formation of the complex. This is actually observed (Table XIII), and the observations strongly support the formation of the complex $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_7$.

FIG 3

0,300

FIG. 4

It is further observed that the discrepancy between the observed and theoretical titre values for the formation of the compound $KCd_{10}(Fe^{III}Cy_6)_7$ is, in general, much less than what had been observed in the case of cadmium ferrocyanide (Part IV, *loc. cit.*). Ferricyanic acid is a stronger acid than ferrocyanic acid and hence metallic ferricyanides will, as a rule, be much less hydrolysable than the corresponding ferrocyanides. This is revealed in Table XIII when the theoretical and observed titre values become almost identical in aqueous-alcoholic medium.

The adsorption of Cd^{++} and $(FeCy_6)^{--}$ ions by the precipitated complex would also affect the theoretical titre values. In the reverse titrations cadmium sulphate being in the thermos flask, the titrations are carried out in presence of excess of cadmium sulphate, and hence the chances of adsorption of Cd^{++} ions are greater. Therefore, its effect in aqueous medium would be to lower the observed titre values; and in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol a slight increase in the observed titre values will take place, because of less adsorption in the aqueous-alcoholic medium. This has been actually observed. (Table XIII). In the direct titrations the chances of adsorption of $(FeCy_6)^{--}$ are greater than Cd^{++} ions, and hence the observed titre values should be lower than the theoretical one. But experimentally the titre values of cadmium sulphate observed are 27.4 to 27.6 c. c. as against 27.1 c. c. [theoretical

value for the formation of the compound $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_7$. From the specific nature of the adsorptive properties it may be possible that Cd^{++} ions are adsorbed more than $(\text{FeCy}_6)^{3+}$ ions, and thus the discrepancy of the titre values can be explained.

The experiments on hydrolysis and adsorption are in progress, and will be communicated in a later issue.

Thus, on the basis of the thermometric and conductometric results conclusive evidence for the formation of the compound $\text{KCd}_{10}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_7$ is obtained.

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. S. S. Deshapande for his kind interest in the progress of this work, and also to Dr. K. C. Mehta, Principal Agra College, for the grant of a Research Fellowship to one of the authors (H. C. Gaur).

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Received July, 8, 1948.